

The Data Profile – Full Facilitation Guide

The data profile is a semi-structured asynchronous activity completed by individual participants before group work begins and shared with collaborators to facilitate team bonding. It consists of seven questions organized around a star-shaped diagram (a box-by-box alternative is also available), covering preferred working environment, prior collaborative experience, and personal strengths and challenges. On the following pages, we will provide you with everything you need to set it up and facilitate it as well as some inspiration on how to adapt it to different teaching contexts.

1. Materials, Duration, and Instructions

1.1. Materials

Printed or digitally accessible copies of the data profile handout (star layout and box layout both included at the end of this guide). Make sure that both versions are available to participants so they can choose according to their communicative preferences.

1.2. Duration

Completing the data profile is an asynchronous task: participants can take as long as they need to prepare on their own. Sharing in a group takes approximately one hour for a group of five. We suggest structuring this in two rounds: a faster round through questions 1-5 (roughly one minute per participant per question), followed by a slower round dedicated to questions 6 and 7, where reflection on group dynamics and their triggers tends to generate the richest discussion.

1.3 Written instructions

Written instructions are provided in the printable and / or shareable handout included at the end of this guide.

1.4 Oral Instructions

- Inform participants that they have been given a data profile handout to complete before the session and possibly bring with them to share with the group.
- Let participants know responses can take the form of words, symbols, drawings, etc. and that there are no right or wrong answers.
- Clarify that participants need not answer all questions and are free to share only what they feel comfortable disclosing.
- Point participants to the seven categories included on the first page of the data profile handout and the appendices at the end of the sheet, which offer pattern vocabulary to assist with questions 5, 6 and 7, reminding them they are still free to use their own language.
 - Clarify that the patterns listed are not personal attributes but tendencies that become available in group processes as a whole. Participants

should therefore reflect on the patterns they have seen themselves or others falling into, as well as the circumstances that prompted these.

- Remind participants they can use the notes box at the bottom of the handout to record any similarities or differences they have identified between their answers and those of the other participants, and what these might mean for collaborative work.

1.5. Reflection Questions

Responses are shared in a facilitated round proceeding question by question rather than person by person, in order to encourage more effective comparison between participants. Once responses to some or all seven questions have been shared, invite participants to reflect together; they can use the notes box at the bottom of their sheet.

- What similarities or differences do you notice?
- What might these mean for how you collaborate on the task at hand?
- Is there anything you would like to offer or request before group work begins?

1.6. Advice for Contextual Adaptations

The data profile attached was developed to facilitate collaborative academic writing, which is why the seven categories focus on writing environments, modes, and relationships. It can, however, be adapted to different collaborative tasks by replacing its content with questions relevant to the activity at hand. The key is to maintain the questions domain-specific and focus on participants' contributions to the shared work.

A few final observations:

- **Group size:** We found that the activity works best in groups of up to five participants. For larger groups, consider running it in subgroups before all participants are brought together for a plenary comparison.
- **Repeated use:** The data profile was not designed as a conversation starter only. For example, it might be used at the end of a collaboration to compare how participants' original profiles actually unfolded throughout a project, making it a tool for both individual and group reflective practice.
- **Patterns vs personal attributes:** The appendices list patterns taken from [1], where they are referred to as "roles"; we use "patterns" instead, as these tendencies are not fixed personal attributes but emerge situationally within group processes. Oral instructions already clarify this distinction to participants. Nevertheless, facilitators should be prepared for the possibility that questions 6 and 7 feel sensitive for participants with negative experiences of group work, and use their judgement about how to create space for selective sharing.
- **Language:** While the use of a shared language is advised to avoid communicative obstacles, participants should feel free to respond in whichever language they are most comfortable, particularly in multilingual groups. Facilitators may consider noting this in the written instructions.

References

1. Johnson SZ, Patterson A. Teaching community in the two-year college: a model for making groups work. *Teach Engl Two-Year Coll.* 2016;43(3):291–306.

Data Profile

A star-shaped self-profile to warm up a collaborative-writing group.

1 My name & where I (prefer to) write

Write your name, then use words or a symbol — *desk, bed, sofa, kitchen table, margins of a book, drafts folder...*

2 The type of things I write (alone or with others)

Words or symbols — reports, feedback, articles, books... Add a ★ for what you do most, a ▼ for what you like best.

3 How much experience I have with collaborative writing

Shade as many columns as fit: **0** never · **1** only when forced during studies · **2** at least one article/report · **3** I co-write regularly · **4** this is the only way I write.

4 Modes of writing-collaboration I have tried

Fill the small triangles with the colour(s) below and ★ your preferred mode.

- **Red** — **Layering**: one person writes first, the others edit.
- **Orange** — **Combining**: divide chapters, then combine and edit.
- **Yellow** — **Stitching**: divide paragraphs; an author stitches them together.
- **Green** — **Something else** (e.g. letter-writing → article); tell us about it.

5 How I have shown up in (writing) collaborations

Record every pattern you have noticed in yourself — *lead writer, collaborator with own responsibilities, editor, something else* — say what

6 + What I am good at in writing collaborations

A note or symbol. Feel free to borrow language from **Appendix A (Task patterns)** and **Appendix B (Social patterns)**.

7 – Negative experiences I have had in collaborative writing

A note or symbol — e.g. social loafing, time-management conflicts, different writing styles, discrimination, something else. **Appendix C (Patterns that can get in the way)** can help.

How the star maps the 7 questions

Tip — if the star shape feels busy, use the box version on the last page instead.

Pattern inspiration — Appendices A · B · C

The patterns listed below are adapted from [1], where they are referred to as “roles.” We use “patterns” instead, as these tendencies are not fixed personal attributes but emerge situationally within group processes – see the oral instructions for further discussion. Borrow vocabulary from these lists while filling boxes 5, 6, and 7. You are, of course, free to invent your own pattern.

Appendix A — Task Patterns

Contributor / Talker	Provides information, opinions, critiques, analysis.
Seeker	Asks for input from group members to get facts, opinions and clarification
Mover	Prods the group forward in its task, perhaps even pushing the group out of a rut when necessary
Doer	Performs the nuts-and-bolts work that make a group run efficiently by recording, communicating, and arranging details for the rest of the group

Appendix B — Social Maintenance Patterns

Supporter	Offers praise, acceptance, and recognition of others
Harmonizer	Mediates disagreements between group members
Tension reliever	Through humour or another method, allows group members to relax in tense moments
Conciliator	Offers to back down and make amends during conflict
Gatekeeper	Ensures that all members of the group are able to voice their opinion
Feeling Expresser	Makes explicit the mood, feelings, and attitudes of the group.
Follower	Goes along with the group and is game for what others suggest

Appendix C — Patterns that can get in the way

Aggressor	Attacks other members of the group by belittling them
Deserter	Disengages from the group and may participate in side conversations or text/check email.
Blocker	Refuses to cooperate and responds negatively to all suggestions and ideas from other group members
Dominator	Interrupts others and ignores all ideas but own
Recognition Seeker	Embarks on long tangents whose only point seems to be the greatness of the speaker
Joker	Tells inappropriate jokes and jokes at inappropriate times and doesn't recognize when other group members need everyone to work and participate genuinely

Box layout — same questions, no star

A box-by-box alternative for those who prefer a calmer layout.

1 Name & where I (prefer to) write

Name, plus a place or a symbol (desk, bed, sofa, margins of a book, a drafts folder...)

2 What I write

Reports, feedback, articles, books, blog, poetry... ★ most ▼ favourite.

3 Experience with collaborative writing

Shade columns — 0 never · 1 only when forced · 2 a bit · 3 regularly · 4 only way I write.

4 Modes of collaboration I have tried

Layering · Combining · Stitching · Something else. ★ preferred.

5 How I have shown up in collaborations

Lead writer · Collaborator with own responsibilities · Editor · Something else.

6+ What I am good at

A note or symbol. Borrow from Appendix A (Task patterns) & Appendix B (Social patterns).

7- Negative experiences

Social loafing · time-management conflict · differing style · discrimination · other. See Appendix C (Patterns that can get in the way).

★ Notes — after sharing in the group

Based on our similarities, differences and experiences we ...